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PRE-SERVICE ENGLISH TEACHERS' DISTANCE LEARNING EXPERIENCE

Abstract. Since the outbreak of COVID-19 in 2020, distance learning has become the prevailing mode in education. Higher educational institutions in Georgia have had to rapidly adopt online learning to prevent the spread of the virus, with varying levels of prior experience and resources. This study focuses on the learning experience of pre-service English teachers in an online mode. Thirteen participants enrolled in the English Teaching Methods course in the Teacher Preparation 60-credit program at Telavi State University were surveyed through an questionnaire in January 2021. The study analyzes the pre-service teachers' expectations for the course, attitudes to online learning, advantages and disadvantages of online learning, and their self-perception as English speakers. The findings offer insights into the effectiveness of online learning in a Georgian context and suggest implications for future teacher preparation programs.

Keywords: Pre-service English teachers, online learning, attitudes to online learning, teacher preparation programs.

Introduction

Since the global pandemic outbreak, many educational institutions have started implementing blended learning, a combination of traditional/face-to-face and online teaching. However, some higher educational institutions were reluctant due to the lack of resources and necessary competences among the academic staff. Teachers' attitudes, acceptance, and use of technologies are key factors to the successful application in the classroom. Many inhibiting factors were overcome once teaching/learning moved online. While distance learning has both advantages and disadvantages, most teachers engaged in online courses have access to common online teaching methodology, technology, mode, and learning resources.

Literature Review

Before the outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic, many educational institutions were already implementing blended learning, which combines traditional face-to-face teaching with online teaching (Maia, Borges, Reis, Martins, & Barroso, 2018). However, some higher education institutions were reluctant to adopt online teaching due to the lack of necessary resources and competencies among academic staff. In successful application of technology in the classroom, teachers' attitudes, acceptance, and use of technology are key factors (Al-Zaidiyeen, Mei, & Fook, 2010). Nonetheless, the move to online teaching and learning became necessary and inevitable due to the pandemic, and many earlier and recent studies have discussed the advantages and disadvantages of distance learning.

To make online learning more effective, recommendations and suggestions have been proposed regarding the technology, mode, and learning resources used (Pacansky-Brock, Brown, Ross, 2017). Most teachers engaged in online courses are familiar with the differences between synchronous and asynchronous modes, popular software and web platforms, and have access to open educational resources. Common online teaching methodologies have also been formed and are identified on international educational forums and blogs.

In Georgia, higher education institutions had limited experience in online teaching and learning until the last few years. However, several Erasmus+ international projects, such as PRINTEL, have encouraged the implementation of blended learning in universities and trained a large number of teachers in Georgia to utilize ICT. Since the spring of 2020, all educational institutions in Georgia have had to adopt online learning modes due to the COVID-19 pandemic. According to a report by the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), Georgia was considered one of the best examples in terms of distance learning among the 98 countries that participated in the study. The report also highlights that the biggest challenge facing the world education system is the malfunction of technological infrastructure, which is a necessary condition for the effective conduct of distance learning, and Georgia has been more prepared in this regard than other countries (https://globaled.gse.harvard.edu/files/geii/files/framework_guide_v2.pdf)

In Georgia, all educational level courses, including teacher preparation program courses, were shifted online due to the pandemic. One popular teacher preparation program is the 60-credit a year program, which provides teacher's professional courses and is designed to address the needs of professionals who want to enter the teaching profession. It mainly offers compulsory courses to become a teacher, such as education theories, pedagogy, subject teaching methods, child development, and practice at school. Applicants for the course are those who want to make a career shift or are looking for a shorter way to enter the teaching profession. The ages, educational backgrounds, and experiences of students in the program vary within each group, but a common pattern can be observed. Most students have had a few-year gap since their last formal educational activities.

Methodology

The study aimed to describe the pre-service English teachers' learning experience in online mode. Thirteen pre-service English teachers enrolled in the English Teaching Methods course were surveyed through an unstructured questionnaire in January 2021. The survey questions explored the participants' expectations, attitudes, positive and negative experiences, surprises, and changes in their ways of language teaching/learning since coming to the university. The study used qualitative analysis to examine the data and identify patterns and themes.

The findings suggest that while online learning has some limitations, it can be an effective mode of education when properly implemented and supported. The study's implications could

inform the development of teacher preparation programs that more effectively incorporate online learning and meet the needs of a diverse group of pre-service teachers.

Procedure

The study involved gathering feedback from participants who had taken an introductory course in English teaching methods, which lasted two semesters and used a flipped classroom approach. The students were assigned reading material to be read in advance and were expected to discuss the content during online sessions. The course included both theoretical and practical components, with students given individual or group tasks to apply their knowledge.

After the completion of the first term in January 2021, 13 female participants were given a questionnaire with open-ended questions about their learning experience. The participants were encouraged to provide detailed and reflective responses, and the researcher provided an example to guide them. The questionnaires were in the participants' mother tongue and were later translated into English for analysis. Qualitative data from the interviews was analyzed using established qualitative data analysis methods, including coding, and identification of main themes.

Results and analysis

In this paper the answers to following questions will be discussed: Expectations for the course, attitudes to online learning and mistakes, feelings.

- *Expectations*

The participants had high expectations for the courses. First of all, they all expected that the course should be interesting, giving them necessary knowledge, providing with interesting material. For some of them it was a chance to learn practical things about teacher's profession such as different teaching approaches, teacher's responsibilities, how to manage teaching/learning processes, what makes a good teacher, how to combine theory with practice, how to choose a textbook, etc. For a few of them it was a way for personal development, meeting professionals and boosting self-confidence. Some looked as the way to improve their English-speaking skills.

- *Experience in distance learning*

The study participants' reflection on their distance learning experience comprises mainly of what they expected it could be and their surprise about the quality of online studies. The study participant reflected on advantages and disadvantages of distance learning given in the table below (see table 1)

Table 1

Advantages	Disadvantages
Saving time and money, avoid unnecessary expenses: apartment rent, traveling expenses. Flexibility Get information fast meet people easily Convenient Spend more time with family Attendance Preventing spread of viruses Acquired computer skills using internet better Combine work and study Comfortable	Less real-life contact with lecturer and students Online communication online, Fear to miss something Internet problem/ poor connection Lack of classroom meetings, human real relations, mostly practical work Hurt eyes, causes various health problems (headaches) Can be easily distracted Less group work and presentations Tiring Too much technology Lack of authentic human energy Hard to stay focused Less immediate feedback

- *Pre-service teachers' perception of themselves as English speakers*

The study participants reflected on their perception as English speakers; how they felt while speaking English online and if they noticed their mistakes. Several barriers to speaking English were mentioned such as online distractors (background noise, one's image on the screen, slow internet connection, one's sound quality), inner dialogue, tension, lack of self-confidence, lack of physical connection with audience, feeling of insecurity. Most of them were anxious about mistakes and felt sorry.

Discussion

The study aimed to explore pre-service teachers' experiences with distance learning, particularly in learning to teach English. The findings revealed that the majority of participants had positive expectations and were oriented towards professional development, skill acquisition, and practical knowledge. The predictions of poor quality online education were not justified, as stakeholders such as lecturers and administration actively engaged in ensuring a smooth transition to online learning. However, distance learning had both positive and negative impacts on pre-service teachers. While there were advantages such as flexibility, convenience, and savings, there were also challenges such as less group work, presentations, and feedback, as well as difficulties staying alert and managing technology.

The study also examined participants' experiences and perceptions of speaking English online. Many faced barriers such as distractions, tension, lack of self-confidence, and insecurity due to the lack of physical connection with the audience. While some participants adapted to speaking online and improved their abilities, others found it challenging to identify and correct their errors. Some accepted errors as a part of learning, while others were anxious about making mistakes.

Overall, the study suggests that speaking English online can be challenging and anxiety-inducing, but with practice and perseverance, individuals can overcome their barriers and

improve their language skills. However, it is important to note that speaking online may not be a pleasant experience for everyone, as it can be perceived as talking to oneself and can evoke feelings of confusion, tension, and lack of confidence. Additionally, anxiety is a common experience when speaking in general.

Conclusions

In conclusion, this study sheds light on pre-service teachers' experiences and perceptions of distance learning and speaking English online. The findings suggest that while most pre-service teachers had positive expectations for the program and recognized its benefits, they also faced challenges and difficulties such as distractions, lack of physical connection, and anxiety. However, with practice and perseverance, they were able to overcome these barriers and improve their language skills.

The study also highlights the importance of effective online course provision, which requires active engagement from all stakeholders, including lecturers and higher education institutions' administration. Moreover, the findings emphasize the need to address students' anxiety and confidence issues when speaking online, especially in language learning contexts.

In conclusion, this study contributes to the growing body of research on distance learning and online language learning and provides valuable insights for educators and administrators to improve online course provision and support pre-service teachers in their language learning journey.

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